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Evidence-Based Practice in Neurofeedback. A Historical Perspective

Abstract: *Neurofeedback is an evidence-based, non-invasive method of personalized self-regulation of brain function through real-time feedback to improve brain wave activity. It is used to influence the symptoms of epilepsy, Attention Deficit and Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder, post-stroke language disorders (aphasia), traumatic brain injury, chronic pain, depression, autism, sleep disorders, stuttering, dyslexia and dysgraphia etc., as well as to improve memory and cognitive processes. It has been applied successfully to improve memory and cognitive processes, confidence, motivation, stimulate creative processes, as well as to train for sports excellence. The purpose of this article is to provide a historical retrospective of the development of the Neurofeedback paradigm and its contemporary application in the diagnosis and treatment of various types of disorders. The method used is a review of published articles in electronic databases such as Pub Med, Scopus, Web of Knowledge, EbscoHost, using the keywords Historical perspective, Neurofeedback, Evidence-Based Practice, swLORETA.*

Keywords: *Evidence-Based Practice; Neurofeedback; Historical perspective; swLORETA.*

Introduction

The scientific conception of the brain has completely changed over the course of the last decade and the principles of neuroplasticity have now been proven. The brain can change at any age and we can create new neurons throughout our lives. The natural mechanisms underlying Neurofeedback are now becoming clear. Some research has proven relationships of correlation among the central nervous system, the autoimmune system, emotional, physical and mental health. Today, with the advancement of brain-computer interface and the development of brain-wave monitoring technology (swLORETA), Neurofeedback is being used not only for therapy, but also for peak performance by professional sports teams, Olympic athletes and business people.

Neurofeedback is an evidence-based, non-invasive method of personalized self-regulation of brain function through real-time feedback to improve brain wave activity. It is used to influence the symptoms of epilepsy, Attention Deficit and Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder, post-stroke language disorders (aphasia), traumatic brain injury, chronic pain, depression, autism, sleep disorders, stuttering, dyslexia and dysgraphia etc., as well as to improve memory and cognitive processes. It has been applied successfully to improve memory and cognitive processes, confidence, motivation, stimulate creative processes, as well as to train for sports excellence.

The purpose of this article is to provide a historical retrospective of the development of the Neurofeedback paradigm and its contemporary application in the diagnosis and treatment of various types of disorders. The method used is a review of published articles in electronic databases such as Pub Med, Scopus, Web of Knowledge, EbscoHost, using the keywords Historical perspective, Neurofeedback, Evidence-Based Practice, swLORETA.

The historical antecedent for the development of Neurofeedback begins with the conditioned physiological reflexes in the conventional school of Pavlov and his student Kupalov (in the early 20th century), referred to in the Western school by Skinner as "operant conditioning or instrumental conditioning", then proceeds through Anokhin (1935) who developed the theory of functional systems, and ends up with Dr. Kamiya and Dr. Sherman who at the same time (1969 – 1989) discovered that with a simple reward system people can learn to change their brain activity and voluntarily control their alpha waves. This was the first ever EEG Neurofeedback training.

Dark Ages (1898 – 1960): the experiments of Pavlov, Thorndike and Skinner

Pavlov's fundamental discoveries about reflexes provoked the rapid development of behaviourism as a branch of psychology. The basic idea of "stimulus-response" postulates that behaviour (reaction, response) is triggered by some stimulus in the environment of the living organism. To understand this relationship, the term "operant conditioning" or "instrumental conditioning" is introduced. In 1935 the Russian scientist Peter Anokhin, who was Pavlov and Bekhterev's student, developed the theory of the functional system as a unit of integrative activity of the whole organism, where the "action acceptor" evaluates each preceding stage and the degree of usefulness for the organism, i.e. the feedback. Only this

chain of "positive results" of compensation ensure full restoration of lost function (Homsкая 1984: 28).

The American psychologist Edward Thorndike, an expert in the field of educational psychology, is considered the first behaviourist. He formulated the law of effect in 1898, which states that a living organism responds to a situation in accordance with the possible outcome that they can obtain. There are two possibilities:

1. In case of a positive result - the living organism remembers it and will most likely repeat their response in any subsequent similar situation.
2. In case of a negative result - the response is not remembered, and to avoid repeating it, the organism never again responds as they did the first time.

The most important thing about the Law of Effect is that the relationship between stimulus and response is a neural relationship, and it is this relationship that is learned and remembered in memory. The more repetitions of the stimulus-response relationship are made, the stronger and more stable it becomes. Later, Thorndike further developed the Law of Effect with new parameters - how many repetitions are needed to remember the positive or negative result, when the proper time is to give the possible reward to reach the response sought, and how long it would take the living organism to forget their previous response. Applying the law of effect to human experiments, he focused on human intelligence. It is, he argued, based on established neural connections and depends not only on genetic factors but also on personal experience. He therefore paid close attention to the so-called "learning environment", which plays a crucial role in learning and reinforcing desired behaviour (Thatcher & Lubar 2008).

Grey Ages: the late 1950s and early 1960s: Semyon Korsakov, Nikolai Vasilevski, Natalia Chernigovskaya, Dr. Joe Kamiya Dr. Barry Sterman Elmer Green

Post-war medicine has left a significant legacy in medical science, including in the field of electroencephalography (EEG), and has played an essential role in improving the diagnosis and treatment of various neurological conditions. After World War II the Soviet Union was one of the leading centres for EEG research and continued to play an important role in the development of this science for decades.

Representative of this period is Semyon Korsakov, who was one of the first scientists in the Soviet Union to apply EEG in neuropsychology.

Soviet scientists successfully applied EEG techniques to research in various fields such as neurology, psychiatry, psychology and neuropsychophysiology in the post-war period (Tsekov, et al. 2017). Around the same time in San Francisco Dr. Joe Kamiya at the University of California discovered that persons could learn to voluntarily control their own alpha waves.

There are three founders of the Neurofeedback method: Dr. Joe Kamiya at the University of Chicago (1950s – 1960s), Dr. Barry Sterman at the University of California in Los Angeles, and Elmer Green at Menninger Clinic in Topeka, Kansas who shortly afterwards built on the achievements to date with his own method. Dr. Kamiya set up experiments following Pavlov's theory, and developed a reward system that altered participants' brainwave patterns. He investigated the relationship between alpha waves and anxiety, displaying results in real time using EEG.

Dr. Sterman began working with cats to determine if they could self-regulate their Sensory Motor Rhythm (SMR). Using a simple reward system cats receive rewards when they change their brain waves to a set frequency. Through a specially designed machine they receive a food kibble every time they "get it right", and thus quickly learn to control their brain waves to receive the tasty food. Dr. Sterman's experiments also focus on open-eye training to induce sensory motor rhythm (SMR), which was initially shown to be effective in the treatment of seizure disorder, which was later confirmed in Joel Lubar's research with ADHD. In 1969 the method of brain self-regulation through EEG and other physiological parameters was officially named biofeedback.

Elmer Green explores alpha theta (AT) training, which has been used to impact addictions, post-traumatic stress disorder, personality integration, and even training for excellence. At the time these methods were often referred to as fast wave training (Sterman's method) and slow wave training (Kamiya and Green's method) (Crane & Soutar 2000). These approaches are foundational to standard and traditional NFB and most of the published literature written to date reflects research on these basic methods (Thatcher & Lubar 2008).

NASA Space Programme

The results of the two experiments attract NASA's attention, where Dr Sterman is tasked with examining how exposure to toxic rocket fuel causes an epileptic reaction in humans. During the initial experiments the negative side effects of the fuel became apparent to all with the exception

of ten of the cats used in his initial experiments. It became clear that the effect of SMR brainwave training created "stable" brains that were resistant to acute epilepsy. By applying this Neurofeedback training to the astronauts he was able to reduce the onset of epileptic reactions in 60% of the participants and the effect was long lasting. As a result, this type of training is still used by NASA for all astronaut missions and Neurofeedback became an alternative medical treatment for epilepsy more broadly.

A few years later Dr Sterman did an experiment for NASA, again using the cats from his lab. This time he tested the effects of exposure to fuel from the lunar module. Most of the cats showed a linear progression of brain instability with increasing levels of toxic fumes; first drowsiness, then headaches, followed by hallucinations, seizures, and finally death. Sterman noticed that the cats that did not respond to the toxic fumes were the same ones he had used in the SMR brain training experiment a few years earlier. SMR training gave these cats extremely "stable" brains. Sterman continued to train SMR in humans to control their epilepsy – 60% of the participants reduced their seizure levels and the results were permanent.

This has resulted in NASA continuing to train its lunar astronauts to control the SMR rhythms in their brains. Moreover, more than fifty years later, Neurofeedback is still part of the astronaut training program (Thatcher & Lubar 2008; Thatcher 2011).

The 1970's Grey Ages

Nikolai Vasilevski continued to develop the Russian school of physiology, and in the late 1960s and early 1970s he began the research on neural feedback at the cellular level as a principle of regulation. Natalia Chernigovskaya started to apply the biofeedback method to the treatment of certain neurological and psychiatric diseases. Her goal was to train the brain or muscles in patients with cerebral palsy using physiological parameters such as biofeedback- EEG rhythms, muscle electrical activity and slow metabolic processes. EEG feedback (neurotherapy) was applied to the treatment of neuroses and epilepsy, as well as post-traumatic injury recovery of Vietnam War veterans, by modulating Theta rhythms. In Europe, German scientists under the leadership of Niels Bierbaum began to apply slow rhythms (Theta and Delta) to treat epilepsy and schizophrenia (Kropotov 2010; Thatcher 2011). In the mid 70's Neurofeedback came to the attention of people from various religious communities who wanted to gain spiritual development through meditation. Neurofeedback thus found itself caught between science and reli-

gion and acquired a dubious reputation as a meditative or spiritual tool, which, given the extreme prejudices of the time, made it unpopular with researchers seeking career advancement. However, it was in these years that scientists began to explore Neurofeedback relationship to new research and findings about brain plasticity.

From the 1990s to the present day – *the Renaissance years*

Although in the late 1980s Neurofeedback was on the "fringes of science", the evidence of its effectiveness continued to be published. Scientists, began experiments to establish the extent to which this therapy could be used for other central nervous disorders and in particular ADD. In addition, research into Neurofeedback and epilepsy is continuing. In the 1990s Neurofeedback started to be promising in dealing with a wide range of conditions and more experiments were carried out on its effects on a spectrum of disorders such as ADHD and even autism. At the beginning of the century, bearing in mind that there existed a better understanding of the underlying mechanisms in the brain, Neurofeedback moved from an experimental phase to the direct treatment of various conditions. Numerous medical facilities now offer Neurofeedback as an alternative medical treatment for ADD and ADHD, as well as for epilepsy and other conditions.

The scientific conception of the brain has completely changed over the last decade and the principles of neuroplasticity have now been proven. Neuroscience has now accepted the correlation among the central nervous system, the autoimmune system, emotional, physical and mental health. Indeed, it acknowledges that the brain can change at any age and we can create new neurons throughout our lives. The natural mechanisms underlying Neurofeedback are now becoming explicitly clear.

In 1989 the United States Congress through Resolution 174 declared the 1990s as the "decade of the brain" and provided funds for the study of the brain through innovative technologies. Due to positron emission tomography (PET) researchers have been able to observe the effects of certain stimuli on brain structure and the corresponding specific brain responses, the so-called "glow areas" (Etkin et al. 2005; Ivey et al. 2017).

In 2008 the U.S. National Institute of Mental Health funded research to identify neurobiological markers in different types of pathology (Cuthbert, 2014). This new strategic plan aims to "identify links between aberrations in fundamental neural networks and functional impairment - with a focus on neurodevelopmental trajectories and environmental factors."

In 2013 President Obama launched the Brain Research through Advancing Innovative Neurotechnologies (BRAIN) initiative (National Institutes of Health 2014). The BRAIN initiative aims to bring together researchers from different disciplines to develop new technologies to study and understand the brain in the hope of discovering the causes of neurocognitive, neurodevelopmental, and other brain-related disorders.

Major funding and research organizations, government bodies and accrediting bodies are recognizing and promoting a better understanding of the role of neuroscience principles in mental health.

What is Neurofeedback?

Neurofeedback is a scientifically proven non-invasive form of brain training. It uses the principles of operant conditioning and neuroplasticity, allowing the brain's natural ability to adapt and form new neural networks to improve quality of life.

Thatcher & Lubar define EEG biofeedback (also called Neurofeedback) as:

Quantitative EEG (qEEG) involves the use of computers to precisely quantify electrical potentials of approximately 1–300 Hz, representing subsecond measures of summated local field potentials generated in groups of cortical pyramidal neurons. (2008: 2)

The activity of brain neurons provide unique information about how the brain functions. When neurons are activated, they produce electrical impulses. By placing electrodes on the scalp the brain's electrical activity, known as EEG, can be recorded. The EEG is generated by a specific type of synchronous activity of neurons that are known as pyramidal neurons. Different types of electrical activity (brain waves) can be recorded by their amplitudes and frequencies. The frequency indicates how fast the waves oscillate, which is measured by the number of waves per second (Hz), while the amplitude represents the strength of these waves measured by microvolts (μV) (Marzbani et al. 2016). To obtain useful feedback information from the unprocessed EEG signal, it is necessary to subject it to some processing. This consists of mathematical operations which are performed by hardware and software, providing an appropriate measurement of the relevant EEG parameters. It is important that the signal processing is conducted in "real time", meaning that the resulting information must be calculated and provided quickly (typically within less than 1/10th of a second). The most common signal transfor-

mation is the Fourier one (Kropotov 2010; Dempster 2012; Tsekov, et al. 2017).

As a result of these and earlier studies (Heinrich et al. 2004; Strehl et al. 2006; Leins et al. 2007; Gani et al. 2008; Arns et al. 2009; Gevensleben et al. 2010; Duric et al. 2012; Li et al. 2013; Meisel et al. 2013; Christiansen et al. 2014) and with the evidence assessment guidelines developed by the APA, "standard" Neurofeedback protocols are considered "Efficacious and Specific, Level V" in the treatment of ADHD (Arns et al. 2016).

Neurofeedback has been used successfully in the treatment of anxiety, depression, post-traumatic stress disorder, obsessive compulsive disorder, ADHD, autism, insomnia, traumatic brain injury, and to impact cognitive problems associated with COVID-19 (Thornton and Carmody, 2005; Coben and Myers, 2010; Coben et al., 2014, 2015; Coben et al., 2019; Kostadinova et al., 2022).

What is swLORETA z-score Neurofeedback.

As technology advances in each field more innovative approaches are available, including for Neurofeedback methods, such as 19 channel Z-score Neurofeedback (ZNFB), swLORETA z-score Neurofeedback and 3-D LORETA Neurofeedback (with or without Z-scores; LNFB).

LORETA and swLORETA are methods that use the solution of the Inverse problem, whose algorithm uses an "inverse solution" to obtain feedback from deeper structures in the brain, such as the singulate gyrus or insula. This is achieved with the two mathematical models - Discrete parametric analysis and distributed non-parametric analysis.

Both methods enable three-dimensional spatial localization of brain activity. Discrete parametric analysis is the basis of many EEG software such as MUSIC, BESA, FINES, EPIFOCUS. These software programmes are effective in localizing epileptic lesions and brain tumors, while the increase in electrodes leads to more precise localization.

Distributed non-parametric analysis is the basis of software programmes such as LORETA, sLORETA, eLORETA, swLORETA, LAURA, FOCUS, VARETA, ELECTRA. These software programmes are extremely suitable for the dynamic research of cognitive and behavioural processes and disorders. However, a larger number of electrodes does not mean greater localization precision. In their clinical comparison swLORETA has the most precise localization ability.

For functional differentiation in neural network architectonics, the terms Modules, Hubs, Nodules, Rich club, Feeder, Local were introduced.

- Nodule (Node). A basic structural unit of a neural network that is always connected to other nodules (nodes).
- Link (edge), a neural connection linking two nodules. Axons are the connections between neurons. The importance of a nodule is determined by the number of adjacent nodules connected to it.
- A module is a group of nodules maintaining intense connections with each other and weaker connections with nodules outside their module. Networks with a high degree of modularity have intense connectivity of nodules within them and limited connectivity with nodules from other modules.
- Hubs are called brain regions that unite a group of modules. A hub serves as a bridge between two or more networks because it is connected to many nodules in all of them.
- "Rich club" are central hubs of great importance for brain communication. They are energetically expensive as they are highly connected and occupy a privileged position in the network, connecting distant nodes. There are two types of rich club hubs:
 - Hub connectors – they connect different modules. There are three cortical areas that are connector hubs: superior parietal cortex, precuneus, and superior frontal cortex.
 - Provincial hubs – they connect nodes in the same module. There are also three subcortical areas that are provincial hubs: putamen, hippocampus, and thalamus.

70% of Rich club are concentrated in the 3 neural networks: Default mode network and Salience network, Executive network.

- Default mode network – these are the neural structures that are activated when no external sensory information is received. It covers the gyrus cinguli anterior, medial frontal cortex, part of the parietal and temporal cortex. This network is the antipode of the executive network and is sensitive to internal stimuli. It is associated with the processes of self-observation, self-evaluation, meditation.
- Salience network – a neural network composed of medially located brain structures: anterior insula (IA) and anterior cingulate cortex (ACC). It is associated with the processes of dedifferentiation of valuable from non-valuable information about our future be-

haviour. This information comes from internal and external sensory systems.

- Executive control network – the executive network is responsible for regulating thoughts and actions in accordance with internal and external goals. Executive functions include cognitive processes such as attentional control, cognitive inhibition, inhibitory control, working memory, and cognitive flexibility (Laird et al. 2011; Lamichhane and Dhamala 2015; Kolev 2019; Kolev and Hryncheva 2023).

In accordance with the laws of classical and quantum physics, the brain is a unique, highly organized biological phenomenon whose function is to constantly compare discrepancies between the expected and the predicted, between error and correction, with the goal of achieving perfection in a given time interval.

Traditional Neurofeedback uses one or two electrodes that are placed on the scalp to increase or decrease a specific frequency or frequencies. swLORETA z-score Neurofeedback uses 19 electrodes in order to diagnose or train the brain in 3 dimensions. It separates the brain into over 12,000 voxels or pieces and calculates brain activity at these locations. It then compares this data to a normative database to determine which areas in the brain differ from those of the mean values. In this way, a relationship of correlation is established between the symptomatology present in the particular person being studied and the areas in the brain that differ from the normal values.

The hardware was originally developed and used as a medical research tool by one of the world leaders in brain research Dr Robert Thatcher in combination with the pioneers of methods of Neurofeedback, Marty Wuttke, Joel Lubar and others.

QEEG, Full surface, 3-Dimensional Deep Brain Neurofeedback is a top level brain research software. The FDA registered QEEG database (meeting inclusion/exclusion criteria, adequate and transparent sample size per age group, and amplifier) is applied. It has been clinically collated and cross-validated in over 100,000 peer-reviewed publications.

Using a full 19 sensor array, swLORETA z-score Neurofeedback provides a real-time 3D image of brain activity. By means of the 3D image one can train directly deep brain areas and functions; as well as Hagmann's Hubs, Modules, and Default Mode Networks. The symptom checklist is combined with LORETA Z scores measured during a QEEG analysis to help to link symptoms to functional specialization in the brain.

Practically, this means that one can train coherence, processing speed (phase) in all brain regions involved in symptoms as a whole; better imaging and coverage means better performance, which consequently means up to one-third fewer sessions than traditional (individual sensor) Neurofeedback.

swLORETA Neurofeedback Evidence-based medicine

In compliance with evidence assessment guidelines developed by the American Psychological Association (APA) (Arns et al. 2016), efficacy levels for Neurofeedback are:

Level 1: Not Empirically Supported - Immune Function, Eating Disorders;

Level 2: Possibly Efficacious - Autism, Stroke (Cardiovascular Accident), Tinnitus; Depressive Disorders, Mood Disorders, Sleep Disorders, Fibromyalgia/Chronic Fatigue Syndrome, Post-Traumatic, Stress Disorder;

Level 3: Probably Efficacious - Migraine, Insomnia, Chronic Pain, Alcoholism/ Substance Abuse, Headache – Pediatric, Traumatic Brain Injury (TBI);

Level 4: Efficacious – Anxiety, Migraines; Epilepsy, Chronic Pain Headache – Adult Motion Sickness;

- Level 5: Efficacious and Specific – ADHD; Cognitive Impairment;

Thatcher et al. (2020) present a chapter titled "Advances in Electrical Neuroimaging, Brain Networks and Neurofeedback Protocols" in the book "Smart Biofeedback – Perspectives and Applications." They provide an overview of research utilizing z-score EEG biofeedback from 2000 to 2019. The chapter highlights that among the reviewed publications, 32 appeared in peer-reviewed journals, 31 were book chapters or ISNR NeuroConnections publications, and four were reviews and conference presentations. The authors note that no adverse reactions have been published or reported by over 3000 clinicians, six major EEG biofeedback companies, numerous clinics, Veterans Administration and military medical centers, thousands of patients, and more than 60 scientific studies within the last 13 years (Thatcher et al. 2020: 11; Tan, et al. 2009; 2016; Swisher, et al. 2015; Strehl et al. 2006; 2014; 2017; Arns, et al. 2014). To this list 5 more research works could be added from the year 2024: Lin et al (2021); Meeuwssen (2021); Faridi et al (2022); Faridi, et

all (2023); Wu et al (2024); Bink (2016); Coben (2019); Cortese (2016); Leroy (2018); Micoulaud-Franchi (2014).

In Bulgaria biofeedback methods entered in 2012 with the establishment of the "Bulgarian Association of Biofeedback" (in 2019 it was renamed "Balkan Association of Neurofeedback, Biofeedback and Neuromodulation"), and with the training provided by Stani Nenkov and Agnieszka Velichkov-Deinovic. As trainers, they are joined by Stoyan Vezenkov, Radoslav Shterev and Dimitar Kolev. The establishment of the "EEG and Biofeedback Center" at the Faculty of Public Health, Health Care and Sport at the South-West University "Neofit Rilski" in Sofia has made a huge contribution to the popularization of the method. Through participation in various projects more than 10 new teaching disciplines were developed as part of the Bachelor, Master and PhD degree programmes in various faculties. On the clinical application of Biofeedback methods, one PhD thesis has been defended (Goranova 2021) and 3 monographs have been published (Vezenkov, Goranova 2013; Goranova 2021; Sakareva 2022); dozens of articles have been published, publications have appeared in proceedings and journals, and presentations at conferences have been delivered (Vezenkov, Ivanov, Goranova 2011; Vezenkov and Goranova 2013; Vezenkov 2016; Vezenkov & Mitev 2015; Vezenkov & Hadjiev 2017; Goranova 2012, 2015, 2018, 2020, 2021; Goranova, Kostadinova, Vezenkov 2018; Kostadinova, Sakareva, Goranova, Filipova 2022). Exceptional diagnostic, therapeutic and publishing activity with the application of swLORETA has been developed by Dimitar Kolev, PhD (Kolev & Genov 2017; Kolev, Genov & Dilkov 2018; Kolev 2019; Kolev Hrincheva, 2023).

Conclusions

The implementation of real-time z-score Neurofeedback constitutes a pivotal advancement in the realm of neurotherapeutic interventions, facilitating the detection of deviations from established norms. These deviations, manifesting either as aberrant neurological patterns corresponding to specific symptomatic presentations or transient spikes indicative of momentary extreme states, are rendered perceptible through the real-time monitoring and analysis afforded by this innovative technique.

Integral to the efficacy of z-score Neurofeedback is the utilization of normative datasets as a point of reference. By juxtaposing individual neurophysiological profiles against these normative benchmarks, clinicians are empowered to swiftly discern the requisite direction of inter-

vention. Such discernment encompasses the judicious manipulation of threshold values, a strategic manoeuvre aimed at modulating and optimizing the efficiency of cerebral networks implicated in symptomatology. Whether through the augmentation or attenuation of threshold values, this calibrated adjustment serves as a catalyst for the induction of regulatory mechanisms within the neural architecture, thereby fostering a milieu conducive to therapeutic outcomes.

In essence, the integration of normative data within the framework of z-score Neurofeedback engenders a paradigm wherein clinical decision-making is informed by empirical evidence and guided by a nuanced understanding of individual neurobiological idiosyncrasies. By leveraging normative benchmarks as a heuristic compass, clinicians are empowered to navigate the complex terrain of neurotherapeutic interventions with precision and confidence, thereby optimizing patient care and augmenting therapeutic efficacy.

The literature reviewed here emphasizes the effectiveness of electrical neuroimaging in revealing detailed neural activity patterns in the human brain. This includes the precise localization of neural activity, particularly phase shifts and phase locking across different brain areas like Brodmann areas. These patterns can be accurately quantified using advanced techniques such as LORETA and other distributed inverse solutions.

The advent of novel EEG neuroimaging modalities represents a milestone in the evolution of neuroscientific inquiry and clinical practice. Among these innovations, noteworthy advancements include swLORETA Z Score Cross-Frequency Surface Z-Score Neurofeedback, Brain-Computer Interface (BCI) technology, and swBrainSurfer. These methodologies, characterized by their sophistication and computational robustness, hold transformative potential in enhancing the trustworthiness of EEG source localization while facilitating the establishment of causal links between aberrant neural activity and symptomatic presentations in patients.

Of particular significance is the capacity of these cutting-edge techniques to forge connections between observed neurophysiological dysregulation and the clinical symptomatology exhibited by patients. By delineating the intricate network dynamics underpinning pathological states, clinicians can elucidate the etiological underpinnings of diverse neurological disorders, thereby informing targeted therapeutic interventions tailored to the unique neurobiological substrates of individual patients.

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